

NEWSPAPER STYLE AND THE LANGUAGE OF MEDIA

Nomozova Farangiz Zavqiddinovna

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Language is an essential part of our everyday life. It plays central role in all the spheres of life and it is an important tool that sets humans apart from other species. Basically, we use language in order to inform other people about us, about what we feel, what we want and generally, in order to understand and reveal the world around us (importanceoflanguages.com).

The goal of stylistics is not simply to characterize the formal features of texts for their own sake, but to display their functional significance for the interpretation of the text. Sometimes, a question arises, why should people examine stylistics? To examine stylistics means to explore language, and, specifically, to study creativity in language use. Exploring stylistics thereby fertilizes our ways of thinking about language and, as remarked, exploring language offers a essential purchase on our understanding of texts (Simpson 2004:4).

Stylistic devices are typical language mechanisms which authors use to create text that is clear, juicy, and unforgettable. Examples of stylistic devices are alliteration, allusion, climax, hyperbole, irony, metaphor and so on.

Functional stylistics deals with all subdivisions of the language which are newspaper, colloquial style and so on.

Functional styles compile complete system. They are in the process of continuous improvement and enrichment. Some scholars enlarge the scopes of functional styles while others specify them.

If we generalize all the issues raised in the resent studies carried out in the Media language sphere, we can say, that newspaper language study is motivated by the normative -stylistic and functional-stylistic exploration views. If in the first case it is important to reveal the peculiarities of literary language in newspapers, to show literary norm deviations, then in the second case newspaper language and style are seen as an expression of publicistic newspaper style as a type and component of functional style and/or just publicistic newspaper style (Кожин 1982:223).

In the way of its development, oration has shaped its genres, which have its aims, problems and contextual features. "These genres are note-writings, reportages, reports, interviews, messages, articles, theories, reviews and letters. Literary-publicistic styles are widely used, such as allusion, feuilleton, pamphlet" (Черепанов 1971).

It is clear, that in contemporary English media, next to the informational articles there are a lot of publications, where informative articles are merged with publicistic styles. In the same periodic we can see various types of both informative and publicistic styles. But except all these diversities, newspaper style has its lexical, phraseological, stylistic and structural features.

Publicistic style is characterized by coherent and logical syntactical structure, with an expanded system of connectives and careful paragraphing. The individual element is not very obvious. Publicistic style is also characterized by the shortness of expression, sometimes it becomes a principal feature.

Speaking about newspaper style we should hasten to mention that not all the printed materials found in newspapers come under newspaper style. The materials which perform function of informing the reader and provide him with an evaluation of information can be

regarded as belonging to newspaper style. There can be a lot of materials, among them essays, scientific reviews, which does not provide any information. When linguists mention “newspaper style”, they mean informative materials which are typical for only newspapers and not found in other publications (studentguide.ru).

Stylistics, a branch of applied linguistics, is that the study and interpretation of texts of every type and/or speech communication in relevance their linguistic and tonal style, where style is that the particular kind of language employed by different individuals and/or in several situations or settings. For example, or the everyday language, the vernacular, could be used among friends, whereas more formal language, with relevancy grammar, pronunciation or accent, and lexicon or choice of words, is commonly utilized during a cover letter and résumé and while speaking during interview. The English literary system has evolved form of designs easily distinguishable one from another. they don't seem to be homogeneous and be several variants of getting some central point of resemblance or better to say. All integrated by the invariant – i.e. the abstract ideal system.

To attract the reader’s attention to the news, special graphical means are used. British and American papers are notorious for the change of type, specific headlines, space ordering, etc. we discover here an outsized proportion of dates and private names of nations, territories, institutions, individuals. to attain the effect of objectivity and impartiality in rendering some fact or event, most of newspaper information is published anonymously, without the name of the newsman who supplied it, with little or no subjective modality. But the position and attitude of the paper, nonetheless, become clear from the selection not only of subject-matter but also of words denoting international or domestic issues[12;78].

A newspaper is a periodical publication containing written information about current events and is usually typed in black ink with a white or gray background. Newspapers can cover a good style of fields like politics, business, sports and art, and infrequently include materials like opinion columns, weather forecasts, reviews of local services, obituaries, birth notices, crosswords, editorial cartoons, comic strips, and advice columns. Newspapers typically meet four criteria:

A sense of being dwarfed by vast neighbours runs deep in the national psyche, inspiring both fear and pride. In a speech to trade union activists on May Day last year, prime minister Lee Hsien Loong told citizens: “To survive, you have to be exceptional.” The alternative, he warned, was being “pushed around, shoved about, trampled upon; that’s the end of Singapore and the end of us”. The Financial Times, Jeevan Vasagar Analysis This article:

It is logical that journalists are the ones who create news language in newspapers. But according to A. Bell, they are not the only ones who generate news copy but also there are editors, who cut and modify newspaper language to the standards of their newspaper style. So we can conclude that the creation of the newspaper language is very multilayer and complex process in which more than two people are involved in (Bell 1991:7).

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